

SYSTEM OF ENGLISH WORDS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Many words from other regions are entering our lives today as a result of civilization. This article discusses the words that have entered the Uzbek language, their use and syntactic analysis.

Thematic group of assimilations

While English borrowings are in lexical-semantic relationships, such as synonyms and antonyms, they are grouped into thematic groups along with members of a particular paradigm. Such thematic groups are based on hierarchical (hierarchical) relationships in the language.

As the vocabulary of a language evolves in response to changes in society, the role of words in the enrichment of vocabulary plays a primary role.

After independence, the direct assimilation of words into our language will increase. In particular, English language skills are important.

English words in our language can be divided into socio-political, economic, cultural-educational and sports thematic groups. The number of English-speaking subjects in the field of sports has increased so much since independence that it is convenient and appropriate to study them

systematically, separating them from the words of the cultural-educational field. Many of these words are now actively used in oral and written speech as modern layering words. English professions can be classified according to the following thematic groups:

1. Vocabulary of thematic groups in the socio-political sphere;
2. Vocabulary of thematic groups related to the economic sphere;
3. Vocabulary of thematic groups in the field of culture and education;
4. Vocabulary of thematic group on sports.

Many of the assimilations mentioned in our dictionaries are still used in the press today. In particular, many lexemes used in information technology do not have the

recommended variants in Uzbek dictionaries. We think that if necessary, they should be translated into Uzbek and included in our dictionaries in accordance with the nature of our language.

Thematic groups of lexemes can be studied on the basis of different classifications. For example, science, art, maritime, railways, agriculture, handicrafts, construction, trade, medicine, printing, information technology, telegraph, political, economic, cultural, sports and their internal division. lexemes on military, domestic topics have a unique system.

Also food names, beverage names, clothing names, household names, organization names, place names, fabric names, vehicle names, drug names, fuel The names of products and technical equipment also serve to fill the gaps in some thematic groups in the Uzbek lexicon.

Among the English lexemes, science and scientific terms have a special place. In particular, the units of pedagogy, psychology, ethnography, physics, journalism, history, literature, music, linguistics, biology, botany, physiology, dietetics, geography, chemistry, zoology, drawing are also of scientific importance.

Among the English lexemes, the ones related to household and trade are also unique, and the supermarket lexeme has lost its neologism and moved to the modern layer. There are shop, mini-market, supermarket, hypermarket, megamarket, shopping mall (Moll. "Mall" alley) in the nest, and the hypermarket lexeme has a neologism character. Megamarket and mall lexemes are typical

of Russian lexicon and have not been mastered in Uzbek.

These lexemes have a specific spiritual difference, which is the difference between the sale of commercial products, total land area, warehouse area, how many customers can receive at a time, service, number of cash registers, the amount of vendors, the ability to deliver the required amount of products, etc. We can see the difference between the two below.

It is the largest shopping mall with a total area of 1,000 square meters. and 100,000 sq.m. varies from In foreign countries, there is a variant called mall, in which cars are not allowed to drive. The mall is one of the largest shopping malls in the country, with galleries, restaurants, cafes, barbershops and cinemas serving customers.

The next retail space of the hypermarket is 3000 sq.m. and the area of the warehouse is 1000 sq.m. required to be

One of the most common types of retail space, the total area of the supermarket is from 400 sq.m. to 1,500 sq.m. warehouse from 250 sq.m. to 600 sq.m. extends to

Currently, one of the most common types is a minimarket with a floor area of 200 sq.m. from 600 sq.m.

The store is in Arabic and is described in our language as a specially equipped sales room to sell something. In addition to the above, the names of large and small types of shops are also found in our language.

Apparently, there are lexemes such as shopping malls, hypermarkets,

supermarkets, mini-markets, shops, which are considered to be shopping malls. These lexemes form a gradonomic relationship according to their lexical-semantic properties.

English lexemes have a lexical-semantic relationship, mainly with the noun, place, within another category. The hooligan lexeme, which represents the character of human beings, belongs to the adjective group of hooligans, hooligans, bullies, hooligans, and the sentimental lexeme belongs to the lexemes of empty, cheerful, crying, and so on.

Significant changes in the semantics of English words in the Uzbek lexicon are significant. takes a leading role in the process of language events such as active participation.

As the use of English dialects in our language becomes more active, the etymological history of some dialects related to lexical meaning is also of interest to linguists. For example, a pre-independence cowboy [visual. cow-boy <cow - cow + boy - young man] in the western United States; it does not seem unnatural to express the meaning of a brave, courageous young man. Hot-dog, a delicious and light meal for young people, acquired after independence. hot - boiling, hot; and the lexeme dog - it] raises the suspicion that even a person with a basic knowledge of English may have the name of a dish made from dog meat. However, the etymology of food names, which have such a history, requires a large amount of explanation. Hot dogs were used on the Internet in 1884 as a synonym for sausage, and the motto of the sausage makers at the

time was "Love me, love my dog." it is said to have been first mentioned by Berry Popik, and in 1906 to be recognized by the famous cartoonist Thomas Aloysius Dorgan. There are other versions of the etymology of the word hot dog. In short, the hot dog does not have any dog meat at all, but only beef or chicken. The pre-independence cocktail lexeme also has its own etymological history in the English sense cocktail.

Although English dialects come into our language as the names of concepts such as things or events, their etymological history in their own language does not leave anyone indifferent. hooligan hooligan] lexeme on behalf of a famous Irish horse named Houlihan; very small man; dwarf dwarf [visual. Lilliputian] on behalf of the fantastic dwarfs of the imaginary Lilliputian country in the famous writer J. Swift's "Gulliver's Travels"; vatman [ingl. Whatman] on behalf of the paper mill owner J. Watman; hemorrhoids used in medicine [visual. Highmore] on behalf of the English physician and anatomist N. Gaymor; lyuizit [ingl. lewisite] on behalf of the American chemist U. Lewis; makintosh [ingl. Mackintosh] on behalf of the Scottish chemist Mackintosh, who invented the waterproof fabric; rugby used in sports [visual. rugby] on behalf of the English rugby town; badminton [ingl. Bad-minton] on behalf of the city of Badminton in England; reglan [ingl. Reglan] on behalf of the British General Reglan; sheviot [ingl. cheviot] On behalf of the Cheviot Hills, a breed of fine-wool sheep in Scotland; boycott representing political understanding [visual. The lexeme Boycott] is derived from the name of a large English landowner, Ch.K. Boycott, and can be

understood as an extension of the meaning of famous horses to related horses. In general, the names of food products, beverages, clothing names, household items, organization names, place names,

fabric names, vehicle names, drugs, which are available in our lexicon names, names of fuel products, names of technical equipment also serve to fill the gaps in some thematic groups in the Uzbek lexicon.

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